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Data Review

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Abstract

The Belarus Initiative was launched by Chatham House in the aftermath of the mass protests experienced by the country in 2020. Overall, it has conducted 21 surveys among Belarusians living inside the country between late 2020 and late 2025: two in 2020, four in 2021, seven in 2022, four in 2023, two in 2024, and two in 2025. Additional waves may follow. While the surveys include repeated items—such as socio-economic indicators, political preferences, and support for or opposition to the government—each wave also focuses on a specific issue salient at the time of fieldwork.

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Review of the Belarus Initiative Polls

by Stas Gorelik

The Belarus Initiative was launched by Chatham House in the aftermath of the mass protests experienced by the country in 2020. The Belarus Initiative was launched by Chatham House in the aftermath of the mass protests experienced by the country in 2020. Overall, it has conducted 21 surveys among Belarusians living inside the country between late 2020 and late 2025: two in 2020, four in 2021, seven in 2022, four in 2023, two in 2024, and two in 2025. Additional waves may follow. All surveys were administered online among Belarusian urban residents (roughly 80% of the national population).

Each wave relied on a random sample of approximately 600–800 respondents recruited through online advertisements. Some individuals participated in multiple waves, although no information on the resulting panel structure is provided.

While the surveys include repeated items—such as socio-economic indicators, political preferences, and support for or opposition to the government—each wave also focuses on a specific issue salient at the time of fieldwork. These issues have included attitudes toward the West, the Russo-Ukrainian war, and the proposed constitutional referendum. The initiative's [website](#) provides concise summaries of the main findings from each survey, available in both English and Russian.

Despite being a widely used source of data, frequently cited in Belarusian media and policy briefs, the Belarus Initiative surveys exhibit several validity concerns that remain unaddressed by the implementers. No systematic efforts have been made to assess the accuracy of responses to politically sensitive questions or to determine how the samples may differ from the broader urban population. Moreover, a substantial share of respondents select “don’t know” or “hard to say,” especially on political items, which may reflect disengagement or hesitation to answer certain questions due to fear or perceived risk.

Data access: <https://en.belaruspolls.org/>.